

2025 NASA SMD Open Source Science Data Repositories Workshop

Levels of Service - Virtual
August 25, 2025

- Facilitators: Deborah Smith
- Note-Taker: Amelia Pilgrim
- Chat monitor: Cherrelle Tucker

ALL DAY MATERIALS CAN BE FOUND HERE

Agenda

- Visit each of five activity stations in small groups (online visit breakout rooms)
- A bell will ring to signal change to another station - mix up and join a new group
- Levels of Service Model Concept - *Deborah Smith*

Pre-Activity

- Introduce Miro board with thoughts, comments and questions about NASA SMD Level of Service Model Concept

Speaker/Lightning Talk Notes

- Level of Service Model Concepts has been used for years. Only works for NASA Earth Science. Looking to build similar system across SMD.
 - “Basic” - has enough metadata to be discoverable, but not much more than that. User guide but not much beyond
 - “Standard” - supported more by data center
 - “Comprehensive” - more advanced metadata, much more supported
- “The data becomes more processed as you go down the list from raw to gridded”
- All data needs to meet requirements of minimal metadata. Dataset needs to have MM
 - “What does the data steward do to help that data?”
 - Each advancing level adds services, providing outreach or tool to display data
 - Higher levels take more money, time, and resources. Only some data sets can have the highest level of service.

Webex Chat Comments

- What’s NRT data? With a **?

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Q&A

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